

**INFLUENCE OF THE INTERNAL BRANDING FACTORS ON BRAND ENDORSEMENT
IN SERVICE SECTORS OF BANGLADESH: VALIDATING CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK
FROM EMPLOYEES' PERSPECTIVE**

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Abstract

Employees are considered fundamental building blocks in the service sector to uphold service quality and strengthen corporate brand image. Therefore, synchronizing employees' attitudes and behaviors with the corporate brands becomes a critical success factor in a competitive market. The study highlights the significant roles that the employees have in enhancing the brand equity of the organization. As the growing literature of service branding reveals, several researchers investigated the drivers and consequences of internal branding. Nevertheless, it is essential to further examine and explain the various constructs of internal branding and its effect on reinforcing overall organizational brand performance. With this backdrop, this conceptual paper attempts to analyze the internal branding interventions to sway the brand endorsement behavior of professionals in the service industry. By reviewing the relevant concepts pertinent to the paper, this paper proposes six internal branding factors, namely brand knowledge, management support, training, senior leadership, teamwork, and internal communication, which subsequently have been included in a conceptual framework to explore their impact on the brand endorsement further. Through the theoretical appraisal of the associations between the constructs, this study generates scholarly insights that can empirically evaluate to obtain essential managerial insights pertinent to the service industry.

Keywords: Internal branding, brand endorsement, brand knowledge, internal communication, service branding

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1. Introduction

As an indispensable tool to uphold branding strategies, internal branding has attracted research attention from scholars as well as corporate managers around the world. Marketing strategies are devised and implemented, keeping the development of the organizational brand in mind (de Chernatony, 2006). Internal branding encourages employees to become involved with brands, which leads to the development of consistent and enhanced delivery of a brand experience to organizational members, customers, and other stakeholders (Mitchell, 2002). Branding interventions have primarily targeted external audiences, such as customers. However, it is essential to communicate the brand message among the internal members in this competitive edge of global business, like the employees. This is because employees constitute an essential part of the organizational brand, especially in the service sector, and thereby, they mostly impact the brand's positioning in the marketplace (Lee et al., 2014). Hence, employee engagement with the organizational brands and their active role in endorsing the brands are of great significance in overall branding success.

Internal branding helps employees understand the brand vision, act accordingly, and ensure that their actions and decisions reflect the brand philosophy (Piehler, 2018). When the employees' behavior are shaped by the core values of the brand, a sense of passion and belongingness is developed among them towards their jobs and the organization. Thus, they enthusiastically carry out their duties and responsibilities. This implies that for the brand to be successfully positioned in the market, it needs to become alive internally in the Organization (Yang et al., 2015). Emphasizing the firm's fundamental values makes employees realize the necessity of their roles in accomplishing the organizational objectives (King & Grace, 2010). This is accomplished by on-going employee training and development, consistent and dependable internal communication, and coordinated efforts across the organization to disseminate the brand promises and values (Aurand et al., 2005). Thus developing an effective internal branding program enhances employees' knowledge and attachment with the brand, which aids in improving the overall organizational performance in the long run (Kashive & Khanna, 2017).

Internal branding has become increasingly widely recognized as a core organizational strategy in recent years to align workers' workplace behavior with the brand's goal and ensure that customers receive the correct brand experience (Punjaisri and Wilson, 2017). Indeed, the idea of internal branding is more relevant for branding services, where dealing with the inconsistency in "moment of truth" is a crucial constraint (Norman and Dunning, 1984). To overcome this dilemma, the employees need to understand the importance of fulfilling the promise for the customers and thus enhance their overall experience with the brand (Vallaster & Chernatony, 2005). As a result, facilitating the organizational socialization process, assuring internal communication consistency, organizational socialization, and management's commitment towards internal branding is very important in services marketing (de Chernatony and Segal-Horn, 2001).

Eventually, organizational employees are regarded as a fundamental aspect of the service brands where the roles they play ultimately account for developing the brand image (Punjaisri et al., 2008). Moreover, in-service sector, brands provide a more significant potential to build and nurture customer relationships through managing a unique and reliable brand positioning strategy (Lee et al., 2014). To inspire brand-

supporting behavior, it is imperative to maintain a consistent and coherent knowledge of the brand concept and employee's commitment to organizational brands (Vallaster & Chernatony, 2005). To retain the success of internal branding in the long run and internalize its essence in the Organization, Gapp & Merrilees (2006) argued on synchronizing human resources practices in the organization with internal brand management.

The rationale behind this is employees, by their behavior and actions, primarily influence the overall brand performance of the company. Thus, developing successful service brands requires the organization to develop skillful, dedicated, and motivated staff for endorsing the brand to relevant stakeholders (John et al., 2019). Conceptualizing and institutionalizing internal branding is still considered as a conception of further assessment to scholars and practitioners worldwide (Piehler et al., 2018, Barros-Arrieta and García-Cali, 2020). which includes understanding the interplay between the factors of internal branding to sway the organizational employees' brand-oriented behavior (Nataranjan et al., 2017). This research focuses on the theoretical evaluation of internal branding as a significant tool or strategy to encourage employees' intention to endorse the organizational brands. The study is aimed to shed light on the research objectives, (i) to comprehend the influence of internal branding on service employees' brand endorsement behavior. (iii) Identify and explain the internal branding dimensions and factors that drive employees' brand endorsement intentions.

The rest of the study is designed in different parts: section two reviews the prevailing literature related to internal branding and its implications; section three specifies the research methodology. Section four contains analysis and discussions of the study; conclusion and further research dimensions are presented in the next section, the paper ends with the list of reference articles.

2. Literature Review

What is IB & its importance?

The creation of an organization's brand internally as well as externally is vital since organizations with reliable and enduring brand values are likely to be in a better position than organizations with comparatively less communicated and inconsistent brand notions (Mosley, 2007; Iyer et al., 2018). Realizing this, organizations have increasingly focused on a mutual understanding of the brand message and thereby developing a collaborative environment across the organization for the employees to understand the brand philosophy and ensure the fulfillment of the brand promise (Boone, 2000; Judson et al., 2006;). This notion of nurturing employees' behavior to reflect the values of the brand values is commonly known as internal branding (Vallaster & de Chernatony, 2004; Aurand, et al., 2005; Mosley, 2007). The concept is grounded on the fact in service sector, the service providing staffs who represent the organizational identity and brands to the external communities. As such to augment the service experience, the employees need to understand the purpose of the brand and possess the relevant skills to properly deliver the desired brand message.

IB in service sector & IB factors

In service marketing research, the employees have been considered as the foremost element to build a service brand. This has led to the increasing research on the conceptualization and implications of internal branding (Piehler et al., 2018). Service marketing intensely depends on workers' activities and mentalities (de Chernatony and Dall'Olmo Riley, 1997). In this respect, service providers have become a primary focal point for the ensuring the brand performance in every aspect of service encounter. Since they impact clients' image discernment, an assistance association needs to guarantee that its employees convey the help at the quality level guaranteed by its image.

For the successful implementation of internal branding, the company needs to regularly arrange the events and programs, training, motivating, rewarding, and providing equipment and technology that assist the employees in the effective service delivery (Zeithaml et al., 2006). Due to embracing the internal brand management practices, employees' attitude and knowledge of the brand is further developed to meet the organizational goals. Employees are required to be equipped with the proper skills and information, that are essential to the successful execution of their role. In turn, this will increase their understanding on their job performance, that will facilitate to uphold the employee's commitment to the company (Jones et al., 2003).

IB in Bangladesh service sector

As globalization expands, the subject of internal branding has gain popularity, especially as a way for the corporations to retain a competitive edge in the international marketplace. The issue is still evolving in marketing and management studies literature, and many aspects have not been fully explored, including the influence of internal branding interventions to influence the service employees' brand endorsement (Barros-Arrieta and García-Cali, 2020). In this regard, this study attempts to comprehend these concerns considering the service sector in Bangladesh. In Bangladesh, the service sector experienced a sound growth in the last five years, of around six percent since 2015-16 (BBS, 2016). Half of the country's GDP and approximately two-fifths of the employments positions are represented by the growing service sector (Yousuf et al., 2019). The services sector bears a substantial contribution in the development of national and global economy. As the market places have become more competitive over the years, relying on the financial capability and resources are not sufficient to achieve growth and success. In this regard, building the human resources and improving their skills and expertise is an obvious requirement for the companies to attain the desired goals (Samad, 2013). There is an obvious need to build human capital (Holmgren et al., 2003). This study seeks to appraise the factors of internal branding that influence the service employee's organizational brand endorsement. Brand endorsement represents an ideology which indicates the psychological and behavioral support of the employees towards their organization's brand value, even if the situation requires them to perform in a case where the desired service falls outside of their regular official responsibilities.

Internal Branding

While studying the service marketing literature, it has been observed that internal branding has been widely studied by researchers from various parts of the world. Unlike the goods industry, which relies on tangible things to achieve the brand promise, 'people' aspects are the key component to build the brand equity in service sector (Biedenbach et al., 2019). The reason behind this is, the quality of interaction and experience customers' have while receiving the service from the staffs, influences the image of the service

brand (Foster et al., 2010). Internal branding is usually defined as the organizational interventions to view employees as internal clients and thus help them to adapt themselves with the brand culture and organization values (Du Preez & Bendixen, 2015). In this way, it is assumed that internal branding provides employees with a consistent and purposeful vision of the brand so that they act accordingly during the service delivery stage (Choi, 2006).

The widely utilized framework of internal branding which has been noted in the recent studies, was proposed by Burmann and Zeplin (2005). In this sense, the authors hypothesized the concept as a brand-centered phenomenon related to the functions of human resource, brand leadership building and communication activities. Internal branding has an influential impact on the overall organization through instilling the brand's mission among the employees (Aurand et al., 2005), aligning their attitude and behavior accordingly and motivating them to foster brand-oriented performance (Vallaster & de Chernatony, 2006; Keller, 2003). Therefore, it can be assumed that internal branding primarily consists of human resource factors, brand communication activities and brand leadership programs, which altogether, enhance the employees' attachment with the brand and thus raises their performance (Berry, 2000).

Brand Endorsement

While studying the branding interventions in the education sector from Indian and American context, Nataranjan et al., (2017) found that brand understanding and commitment of the employees are significantly influenced by internal branding programs. As a result, employees actively take part in brand endorsement. While employees possess a favorable attitude about their employer organization, they are naturally inspired to get engaged in spreading positive word-of-mouth information regarding the organizational brands (Löhndorf & Diamantopoulos, 2014). This indicates the employees willingly recommend the brands to others (King et al., 2012). Employees' personal advocacy about the organization yields various fruitful results such as better job performance (Akgunduz and Sanli, 2017).

Personal advocacy of employees is associated with many favorable outcomes like enhanced employee performance (Walden & Kingsley-Westerman, 2018), improved financial efficiency in recruitments (Anees-ur-Rehman et al., 2018), and communicating the employment opportunities to potential candidates who can later take part in brand development strategies (Coleman et al., 2015). When the employees embrace the brand values, they get committed to reflect the same image through their actions and as such they feel inspired to express positive information about the brand.

Brand endorsement by the organizational members thus influences the employer brand to flourish as well as employees' engagement in the workplace which is a valuable intangible asset for the organization (Morokane et al., 2016). Hence, organizations must convey well-crafted and reasoned messages about the brand to the staffs and internalize the brand's desired image and support it thoroughly (Miles & Mangold, 2014). Kashive and Khanna (2017) also highlighted the significant role that internal branding plays to uphold the brand endorsement behavior among the organizational employees to influence organizational attractiveness and firm performance.

Management Support

Organizational environment and management support are also essential for internal branding interventions. More focus is needed to comprehend how employees feel about the work environment and organizational culture (Punjaisri & Wilson, 2011). The efficiency of internal branding can be affected by the relationships among the organizational members and senior leaders in management positions, the status of autonomy prevailing in the workplace, employees' perceived availability of performance recognition facilities (Terlav et al., 2016). Effects Internal branding on employee's behaviors and actions are optimum, when they feel satisfied with their work environment (Verčič, 2021). Undeniably, management efforts and commitment towards internal branding are also necessary to create a brand oriented culture in the organization to nurture productive relationships between management officials and the employees at various functional levels of the company (Mahnert and Torres, 2007; Piehler et al., 2015). Also, emphasis should be given to provide suitable job flexibility to the organizational members which will enable them to perform in a manner that augments the service delivery and brand image of the company (Punjaisri et al., 2009).

Given that, internal branding is not meant to be viewed as a separate phenomenon; it is not likely to have effective outcomes in a situation where the workplace and culture is not encouraging the employees to promote the brand values (Ozçelik, 2015). Therefore, internal branding initiatives require a collaborative and inclusive work environment to sustain the organization culture, interactions, brand identity, organizational image and reputation, in total the inclusion of cross-functional aspects in an company (Biedenbach and Manzhynski, 2016). Du Preez and Bendixen (2015) stressed the role of management in promoting effective internal marketing from the organizational perspective. Chiang et al., (2018), suggested that management support is essential to enhance employees' brand oriented behavior and thus enhance their role clarity and brand commitment. Therefore,

H1: Management support has an impact on brand endorsement

Brand knowledge

Employees who retain high brand knowledge are assumed to be the 'intellectual resources in a business. In that sense, employees with a high brand attachment are referred to as the 'emotional assets' (Nataranjan et al., 2017). For an organization to uphold its overall performance and reputation, it is imperative to initiate appropriate strategies for developing the intellectual as well as emotional assets (Biedenbach et al., 2019). The internal branding process requires the dissemination of relevant information from various channels and levels of the company to the service providing staffs so that they can have a clear picture of the mission and purpose of the brands (Ngo et al., 2019). These messages should represent the organization's vision, values and objectives and accordingly communicate to the employees about accomplishing their job responsibilities (Murillo and King, 2019). Sharing brand related knowledge facilitate employees' understanding and cognitive thinking about the brand promotion strategies and the underlying principle behind these from organizational context (Cheung et al., 2014). The study by King et al., (2012) revealed that employees who possess accurate and sufficient brand knowledge can influence their brand endorsement, that is usually accompanied by significant increase in the organizational brand performance. As such,

H2: Employees' brand knowledge influences their brand endorsement behavior

Senior leadership

The senior leaders of the company also play a substantial role in defining and disseminating a precise and sound brand ideologies. This is of great importance to avert an inconsistent and inconclusive vision that will make employees confused and thus create obstacle in building a superior brand image (Vallaster and de Chernatony, 2005). As noted in the research by Burmann and Zeplin (2005), well-built brand leadership results in improving employees' attitude in connection to the brand identity. This makes a vital effect on employees' commitment to the organizational brands. Morhart et al., (2009) opined that in the internal brand management practices, the presence of transformational leadership lowers employee turnover, improves brand performance and encourages brand endorsement behavior of the employees. To be specific, the dynamic brand leaders supports the employees to perform in a collaborative work environment and ensure that employees' contributions in developing the brands are recognized (Lee et al., 2019; Saleem and Iglesias, 2016). On that ground, the leaders communicate the brand philosophy and ensure the fulfillment of brand promise. Considering the workplace diversity and internalization of products and services, organizational leaders are crucial in planning, sharing and implementing the brand's values leading to augmenting employees' brand oriented behavior (Chiang et al., 2018). For that reason, it can be assumed that,

H3: Senior leadership has an impact on brand endorsement

Internal communication & training

Service marketing researchers (Foster et al., 2010; Piehler, 2018) emphasized the fact that on the whole organizational branding efforts need to integrate external marketing programs designed for the customers as well as internal communication strategies to be shared among the service employees.

The examination from the literature on internal communications agrees that viable internal communications has a significant impact on employees' brand commitment and belongingness to the organization (Du Preez & Bendixen, 2015). A study conducted by Papasolomou and Vrontis (2006) on banking sector found that training and communications programs along with internal branding interventions heighten employees' brand loyalty and upholds their brand related job performance. Punjaisri et al., (2009) emphasized the importance of conducting regular training and orientation programs to improve employees' understanding of the brand's purpose and brand development strategies. In order to achieve this, organizational efforts are needed to promote employees' professional expertise. The authors suggested that by conducting brand-oriented training and sharing relevant strategic insights, employees can effectively participate in the fulfillment of brand promise.

In this regard, the management of the company can utilize the feedback from the employees from group meetings, official mails and team briefings that will facilitate to sustain a shared brand understanding (Barros-Arrieta and García-Cali, 2020). Training programs can consist of job related and brand oriented capability development for improving employees' performance to enhance organizational brand equity (Punjaisri, et al., 2009). These strategies not only uphold employees' aptitude to pursue the brand's mission, but also stimulate the emotional attachment and behavioral alignment of the employees with the organizational brands (Iyer et al., 2018).

Not only do these mechanisms enhance employees' ability to deliver on the brand promise, but they also induce employees' identification with, commitment, and loyalty to the brand. This is also evident in the research study by Punjaisri et al., (2009) among the professionals in the Thai hospitality and tourism

industry by emphasizing that training programs and internal communication channels are critical in attaining the internal branding outcomes. Therefore,

H4: Internal communication has an impact on brand endorsement

H5: Training has an impact on brand endorsement

Figure 1 demonstrates the conceptual framework that this study proposes.

Teamwork

In service-oriented firms, co-workers and colleagues play a considerable role in facilitating the organizational socialization programs and promoting the internal branding programs (King & Grace, 2008). Specifically, organizational environment and teamwork opportunities influence the transformation from a new entrant in the organization to becoming a productive member (Merrilees, 2016). Therefore, companies have started to take necessary measures to ensure employee engagement in achieving the organizational goals and create a collaborative a professional environment through a teamwork approach (Chiang et al., 2018). Establishing such measures assists in developing staff productivity and enhancing brand citizenship behavior (Asha & Jyothi, 2013). Moreover, reliable communication among the workforce, enduring relationships with co-workers and customers motivate the service staffs to perform according to the intended brand values (King & Grace, 2010). Considering this, the recent research conceptualizes "teamwork" as an influencing factor to promote employees' brand endorsement behavior.

H6: Teamwork has a positive impact on employees' brand endorsement behavior

3. Conceptual Framework

This part of the paper presents the conceptual framework in figure 1. The independent variable proposed in the study, IB, is indicated at the left side of the diagram. The five core dimensions are presented in particular boxes. As evident here, the dependent variable: BE is highlighted on the right side of figure 1. The framework illustrates the interplay among the independent and dependent variables as reflected by arrow marks given towards BE.

Source: Adopted from Khan, T., Nahar, R. & Manzoor, S., R. (2020)

4. Methodology

Research design

The principal purpose of the paper is to evaluate the factors of Internal Branding and their influence Brand Endorsement of service-oriented organization of Bangladesh. To do that, quantitative research methodology was applied. A field-based survey was undertaken to collect primary data from the respondents that represent the population of the study. Among these study participants, the structured questionnaires were given. For this research instrument, a reliability test was done through calculating the Cronbach's scores (as shown Table 3). In the next stage, the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) test was incorporated through the Varimax rotation Maximum Likelihood to measure whether the observed variables loaded together continued appropriately correlated and whether they met the reliability requirements for this analysis. Lastly, to decide on the nature of associations existing between the dimensions IB and BE, the research applied regression analysis.

Population & Sample

The population was made up of employees from various service-oriented organizations in Bangladesh. The study has been conducted on service professionals in Bangladesh. In each service sector of Bangladesh, survey questionnaire were distributed through random sampling, as shown in the table below. The sample fame of the study includes employees from all levels who are serving in banks, education institutes, telecommunication industry, hospitals, airlines, and Tourism organizations (Entry-Level, mid-Level, and top-level management). Employees from both managerial and non-managerial levels were included as sample respondents.

Table 1: Questionnaire distribution & response received

Service Sector	No. of questionnaire distributed	No. of responses received
1. Banking	50	33
2. Education	50	25
3. Telecommunication	45	24
4. Hospital/Health	40	17
5. Aviation	30	15
6. Travel & Tourism	25	13
Total	240	127

Measures

Measures regarding the major constructs in this study have been proposed from earlier literature. The survey questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section A generated the demographic characteristics of the sample participants. In contrast, next section measured the employees' perception of internal branding interventions and brand endorsement in a seven-point likert scale (as it gives stronger correlations with t-test results) ranging from 'strongly agree, depicted with numeric 7' to 'strongly disagree as represented with 1' (Lewis, 1993). Cronbach Alpha value of survey questionnaire items is more than 0.7, and it is considered an acceptable reliability co-efficient as suggested by Nunally (1978). As independent variables, the research studied management support, senior leadership, brand knowledge, training, teamwork, and internal communication. The dependent variable was brand endorsement. The measuring instrument for IB was adapted from Punjaisri & Wilson (2011), Punjaisri & Wilson (2017), King & Grace (2010), Ahmed et al., (2003), Nataranjan et al., (2017), and the instrument BE was adapted Nataranjan et al., (2017).

Data Collection Procedure and Validation

Two methods have been used: the library method (compilation of literature study) and the field survey method (collection of statistical data). A standard questionnaire was prepared as a data collection tool. A survey was administered to the selected sample by using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaires were personally distributed to the employees, and the completed questionnaires were collected back after one week. Out of 240 questionnaires distributed, 127 were returned, giving a response rate of 53 percent. After screening the data, 113 responses were recorded. Thus, 14 questionnaires were rejected due to missing information. To assess the validity of the questionnaire, face validity method was used. Thus, offering the questionnaire to some faculty members and experts from corporate, their opinions were used about the authenticity of the items of the questionnaire.

The reliability test was performed to affirm the stability and consistency of the data using Cronbach's Alpha. The alpha value for measuring the reliability of the items in the questionnaires was found to be 0.916, which is greater than the acceptable standard of 0.7 recommended by Nunally (1978). The reliability of the questionnaire was also tested using confirmatory factor analysis, the result of which are presented in the finding section of the study.

Data Processing & Analysing technique

Several different methods are also used for data analysis. To this end, firstly, Kolmogorov-smirnov test is used to examine the normal distribution of the data. If the data are normal, the reliability of the questionnaire is assessed by EFA (Exploratory Factor Analysis) using the Varimax Rotation Maximum Likelihood. EFA was used to assess whether the observed variables loaded together continued appropriately correlated. Finally, the research hypotheses are tested based on Linear and Correlation regression and using SPSS software version 20.0.

5. Findings

The results derived from examining the demographic profile of the sample respondents are presented below in Table 2.

Demographic Characteristics	Classes	Frequency	%	Demographic Characteristics	Classes	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	80	70.8%	Education	Graduate	31	27.4%
	Female	33	29.2%		Masters	80	70.8%
Age	20-24	4	3.5%		MPhil/PhD	2	1.8
	25-29	30	26.5%	Total Work Experience	Below 1 Year	8	7.1%
	30-34	36	31.9%		1-3 Years	12	10.6%
	35-39	20	17.7%		3-5 Years	17	15%
	40-44	16	14.2%		5-7 Years	26	23%
	45-49	5	4.4%		8-10 Years	35	31%
	50 Above	2	1.8%		10 Years and Above	15	13.3%
No. of Organization served	1	42	37.2%		Experience in Present Organization	Below 1 Year	13
	2	28	24.8%	1-3 Years		28	24.8%
	3	16	14.2%	3-5 Years		33	29.2%
	4	5	4.4%	5-7 Years		21	18.6%
	5	7	6.2%	8-10 Years		12	10.6%
	6	11	9.7%	Above 10 Years		6	5.3%
	7	2	1.8%	Types of Organization		Bank	31
	8	1	.9%		Educational Institution	22	19.5%
	10	1	.9%		Telecommunication	20	17.7%
	Organization's Position	Entry	34	30.1%	Hospital	16	14.2%
Mid		53	46.9%	Aviation	14	12.4%	
High		26	23%	Travel & Tourism	10	8.8%	

As Table 2 shows, 70.8% of the survey participants are men, and 29.2% are women. It is evident that, the greater majority of the sample (31.95) consists of respondents whose age is between 30 to 34, and a smaller section (1.8%) consists of people with above 50 years of age. Most of the respondents (70.8%) possess a master's degree, whereas only 1.8% have MPhil and PhD degrees. Ph.D. and holders, with 1.8%, constitute the lowest number of the members. Majority of the respondents (31%) have a working experience of 8-10 years, while 7.1% respondents are categorized under the group with working experience below 1 Year. The largest number of organizational respondents belong to the Mid-level

management position (46.9%), and 23% of the respondents are from the top level of management hierarchy. The survey respondents have the highest working experience in the present organization for 3-5 years (29.2%), and only 5.3% respondents have working experience for more than 10 years. Most of the respondent's responses came from the bank (27%), and the lowest responses from Travel & Tourism (8.8%).

Factor Analysis is a significant analysis method in multivariate statistics. It takes on the prominent function of revealing which of the variables clump together to create super-ordinate variables. Each clump or cluster of the correlated variables is a factor, and the relative link of each of the original variables to a factor is known as the variable's factor loading on the factor. According to Hair et al. (1992), variables with higher than 0.30 are considered significant, loadings that are higher than 0.40 are viewed as being more significant, and loadings of 0.50 or higher are regarded as very significant. This study utilized the factor loading cut-off point of 0.50 for retaining the items in the factor analysis. Factors that demonstrated an eigenvalue equivalent to 1 or higher were retained. A result that revealed at least 50% of the total variance was considered as being satisfactory. After the data were analyzed utilizing the Principal Component Analysis with a Varimax rotation, the 27 variables were decreased to eight factors and explained 70.00% of the total variance. Each variable's communality was relatively high.

The study works to identify factors of IB (Internal Branding) affecting BE (Brand Endorsement). EFA method has been calculated on the 27 statements related to dependent variables of BE to identify the degree of correlation among the items of IB. Feathers of EFA checks for the adequacy of sample data and psychometric adequacy of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of Sphericity (Corruble et al., 2003).

Before finalizing factors, as shown in Table 3, 27 of the items were analyzed, and eight factors were retrieved according to the following suitable steps. No items were deleted because of having a value of more than 0.5. Bartlett's test revealed a significant value of .000, which is lower than .05, and the KMO result was .821, which is higher than .50 and thus considered satisfactory. The communalities' values are also within the appropriate ranges.

The communalities demonstrate how much variance the extracted factors account for in each variable. The initial communality value in the principal components analysis is 1. The extracted values reveal the portion of each variable's variance, which the analysis can explain. Variables with values that are higher (> 0.5) are regarded as being well-represented, while variables with values that are lower (< 0.5) are considered as being non-well-represented. This study found that the highest variance of 82% was accounted for "Skill and knowledge development of employees happens as an on-going process in the organization I work for that help in Brand Endorsement (IB15)" as the value was more than 0.5. However, the lowest variance at only 53% was accounted for "The brand mission and its promise are constantly reinforced during the briefing that helps in Brand Endorsement (IB9)" where the value was also more than 0.5.

Table 3 shows all the factors extracted from the analysis along with their eigenvalues, the percent of variance attributable to each factor, and the cumulative variance of the factor. It is obvious that Factor 1 to 8 is significant because the factors that have latent roots or eigenvalues greater than 1 are considered

significant. All factors that have eigenvalues less than 1 are considered insignificant and are ignored. All eight components account for 70.009% of the total variance.

F1 labeled "Internal Communication (IC)" is the first factor that accounts for the most variance (32.2330%), consisting of eight variables. This factor's eigenvalue is 8.702, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the main factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) influenced by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "Excellent communication by management exists within the organization I work for that help in Brand Endorsement, The brand mission and its promise are constantly reinforced during the briefing that help in Brand Endorsement, Skill and knowledge development of employees happens as an on-going process in the organization I work for that help in Brand Endorsement."

The mean values identified for items of IC include 5.95, 5.99, and 6.04, respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses between "Slightly agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of a service organization which leads towards BE.

Table 3 Factor analysis output of Internal Branding (IB)

Factors (Eigenvalues)	Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Loadings	Variances % (Cumulative)	Communalities	Cronbach Alpha
F1: Internal Communication							
F 1 (8.702)	IB9	5.95	.754	.630	32.230%	.530	0.786
	IB10	5.99	.785	.852		.794	
	IB15	6.04	.712	.847		.825	
F2: Training							
F 2 (2.348)	IB16	6.12	.781	.626	40.927 %	.742	0.775
	IB17	6.32	.735	.661		.587	
	IB18	6.25	.774	.723		.695	
	IB19	6.31	.835	.801		.757	
F3: Management Support							
F 3 (1.791)	IB12	5.95	.875	.833	47.561 %	.812	0.805
	IB13	6.07	.894	.744		.752	
	IB14	6.12	.753	.667		.682	
F4: Senior Leadership							
F4 (1.401)	IB25	6.04	.778	.520	52.749%	.677	0.749
	IB26	6.30	.718	.810		.761	
	IB27	6.39	.737	.787		.777	
F5: Teamwork							
F5 (1.290)	IB6	6.15	.793	.664	57.528%	.695	0.763
	IB7	6.28	.725	.615		.582	
	IB8	6.35	.719	.628		.694	

F6: Brand Knowledge							
F6 (1.248)	IB1	5.87	.940	.572	62.150%	.718	0.697
	IB20	6.12	.753	.785		.790	
	IB21	6.06	.899	.666		.796	
F7 (1.103)	IB23	5.81	.941	.749	66.236%	.738	0.669
	IB24	5.69	.814	.814		.736	
F8 (1.019)	IB3	6.00	.756	.735	70.009%	.723	0.569
	IB5	6.30	.801	.503		.647	

F2 labeled "Training (TR)" is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (40.927 %), consisting of four items. This factor's eigenvalue is 2.348, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the foremost factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "The company provided us excellent training about our job that help in Brand Endorsement, The training has enabled me to do job well that help in Brand Endorsement, Training gives me appropriate skills in relation to delivering the brand promise based on the brand standards that help in Brand Endorsement and Supervisor's instructions are valuable in doing better work that help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of TR include 6.12, 6.32, 6.25 and 6.31 respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

F3 labeled "Management Support (MS)" is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (47.561 %), consisting of three items. This factor's eigenvalue is 1.791, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the leading factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "Management of the company regularly interact with employees that help in Brand Endorsement, In the company, cooperation exists between the management & employees that help in Brand Endorsement and My manager is willing to extend themselves in order to help me to perform my job to the best of my ability that help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of MS include 5.95, 6.07 and 6.12, respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "slightly agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

F4 labeled "Senior Leadership (MS)" is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (52.749 %), consisting of three items. This factor's eigenvalue is 1.401, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the leading factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "Management of the company regularly interact with employees that help in Brand Endorsement, Encourage participative communication help in Brand Endorsement and Shape an organizational culture based on brand beliefs help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of MS include 6.04, 6.30 and 6.39 respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

F5 labeled "Team Work (TW)" is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (57.528 %), consisting of three items. This factor's eigenvalue is 1.290, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the leading factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "During the group meeting, I am clearly informed of the brand mission that help in Brand Endorsement, I clearly understand my role in relation to the brand mission, after attending the group meeting Briefing that help in Brand Endorsement and In the company, cooperation exists between the management & employees that help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of TW include 6.04, 6.30 and 6.39 respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

F6 labeled "Brand Knowledge (BK)" is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (62.150 %), consisting of three items. This factor's eigenvalue is 1.248, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the leading factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "I understand how our customers can benefit from our brands that help in Brand Endorsement, I know how our brands are different from our competitors that help in Brand Endorsement and It is clear to me what is promised to our customers by the brands of our company that help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of BK include 5.87, 6.12 and 6.06, respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "slightly agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

F7 is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (66.236 %), consisting of two items. This factor's eigenvalue is 1.103, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the leading factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "Leaders who translate the brand's promise into action help in Brand Endorsement and Facilitate the development of a shared brand understanding for cross-cultural employees help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of F7 include 5.81 and 5.69 respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "slightly agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

F8 is the second factor that accounts for the most variance (70.009 %), consisting of two items. This factor's eigenvalue is 1.019, which demonstrates that this factor is one of the leading factors in explaining the Brand Endorsement (BE) that influence by Internal Branding (IB) among six different service sectors of Bangladesh. It involves the aspects of "My organization values my contribution to its wellbeing that

help in Brand Endorsement and The organization I work for tries to make my job as interesting as possible that help in Brand Endorsement".

The mean values identified for items of F8 include 6.00 and 6.30, respectively. In the range of the 7-point scale, these mean values reveal responses that are between "agree to strongly agree". This result proves that IB is practiced by those six different types of service organization which lead towards BE.

Several research scholars recommended the varying numbers of items per factor ranging from three to five to represent each factor (MacCallum et al., 1999; Raubenheimer, 2004). And also each latent construct must consist of minimum three items for better explanation. That's why the last two factors in Table 3 is not considered as a factor.

The reliability of the scale of each factor are satisfactory, which is mentioned in Table no 3. Internal Communication (0.786), training (0.775), Management Support (0.805), Senior Leadership (0.749) and Team Work (0.763) and Brand Knowledge (0.697) have satisfactory reliabilities suggested by Nunnally (1967). The remaining two factors F7 (0.669) and F8 (0.569) are also has acceptable reliabilities also suggested by Nunnally (1967). On the other hand, as there are strong theoretical support for these items (Punjaisri & Wilson, 2011; Punjaisri & Wilson 2017; Nataranjan et al., 2017; King & Grace , 2010; Ahmed et al., 2003; King & Grace , 2010; Nataranjan et al., 2017), they were taken as they were shown in table 3. These results exhibit small differences as evident from the scale's initial factors structure, the probable reason behind this is the socio-cultural and contextual differences. Nevertheless, the revised factor structure of IB strategies at service-oriented organization of Bangladesh lead towards BE, is still useful for contextual purposes.

The literature review clearly demonstrates that Factors of IB influence BE on service-oriented organizations in many countries globally, including the USA, UK, Thailand, India, and Iran. In addition, a relationship has also been found between IB and BE on hotels, It sector, banks, and Higher Educational Institutions. IB and BE are two of the well-known theories of branding of any product in the academic area.

The six main factors of IB practices in different service sectors of Bangladesh revealed from the EFA are Internal Communication, Training, Management Support, Senior Leadership, Team Work and Brand Knowledge. The multiple regression analysis was subsequently conducted with these six factors of IB as the independent variables and BE as the dependent variable.

Therefore, the basic model for this study is:

$$BE = \alpha + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + \beta_6 x_6 + e$$

Where, BE = Brand Endorement

x1 = Internal Communication

x2 = Training

x3 =Management Support

x4 =Senior Leadership

x5 =Team Work

x6 =Brand Knowledge

And α is constant, $\beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3 \beta_4 \beta_5 \beta_6$ are coefficient, and e is the error term.

The correlation analysis was carried out to measure if any correlations were present between the selected variables. A higher value demonstrates the presence of a strong correlation among the predictors. We observed no strong correlations among the selected variables, as all the correlation coefficients among the IVs are less than 0.50. Further, variance inflexion factor (VIF) is also less than 10, signaling the non-existence of multi-collearity among IVs.

Table 4: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.758 ^a	.574	.550	.478

a. Predictors: (Constant), BK, TR, IC, SL, TW, MS

b. Dependent Variable: BE

The above calculation shows a correlation among Internal Communication, Training, Management Support, Senior Leadership, Team Work, and Brand Knowledge with Brand Endorsement at 5% level of significance the correlation is 75%. Here, the adjusted R square is 0.550, which tells about 55% variation of the dependent variable is explained by independent variables included in this model.

Table 5: ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	32.637	6	5.440	23.823	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.203	106	.228		
	Total	56.840	112			

a. Dependent Variable: BE

b. Predictors: (Constant), BK, TR, IC, SL, TW, MS

The ANOVA informs if the regression equation explains the statistically significant part of the variability in the dependent variable from the variability in the independent variables. The test revealed that the significance level is 0.000 (p = .000), which is less than 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant

relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Thus, it demonstrates that in general, the Brand endorsement (BE) of ix different service sectors of Bangladesh depends on Internal Communication, Training, Management Support, Senior Leadership, Team Work and Brand Knowledge.

Table 6: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.151	.642		.235	.814					
1 IC	.212	.082	.187	2.591	.011	.453	.244	.164	.773	1.294
TR	-.111	.090	-.094	-1.234	.220	.262	-.119	-.078	.691	1.447
MS	.495	.082	.496	6.019	.000	.671	.505	.382	.590	1.694
SL	.040	.092	.035	.429	.669	.389	.042	.027	.608	1.646
TW	.117	.095	.101	1.229	.222	.491	.118	.078	.595	1.680
BK	.217	.083	.208	2.603	.011	.566	.245	.165	.626	1.596

a. Dependent Variable: BE

The multiple regressions were carried out to identify the best combination of Brand Endorsement (BE) predictors among six independent variables Internal Communication, Training, Management Support, Senior Leadership, Team Work, and Brand Knowledge. The coefficients table reveals the significant regression coefficients are Internal Communication ($p=0.011$), Management Support ($p=0.000$) and Brand Knowledge ($p=0.011$) whereas, Training ($p=0.220$), Senior Leadership ($p=0.669$) and Teamwork ($p=0.222$) are not significant. The significance levels of Internal Communication, Management Support, and Brand Knowledge articulate that three variables are exclusively contributed to the regression equation, thereby making a significant contribution to the prediction. But Training, Senior Leadership, and Teamwork do not. Therefore, Brand endorsement on six different service sectors of Bangladesh influences Internal Communication, Management Support, and Brand Knowledge.

In addition, it is also revealed that 1 unit of increase in Internal Communication will influence Brand Endorsement by .212 times, respectively, 1 unit increase in Management Support will influence Brand Endorsement by .495 times, and 1 unit increase in Brand Knowledge will influence Brand Endorsement by .217 times. It has been clearly noted from the VIF and Tolerance value that multicollinearity does not exist as the VIF and Tolerance values are 1.00, which are lower than 10.

Standardized Coefficients also show the most significant variables among all the variables. Internal Communication, Management Support, and Brand Knowledge has the most significant than Training, Senior Leadership, and Teamwork

So the Regression Model is:

$$BE = .151 + .212 * \text{Internal Communication} + .495 * \text{Management Support} + .217 * \text{Brand Knowledge}$$

Internal Branding factors influence the Brand Endorsement

Table 7: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.644 ^a	.415	.410	.547

a. Predictors: (Constant), IBBE

b. Dependent Variable: BE

The fitness model R, R square, and Adjusted R square are measured using the fitness model. It will also assess the intensity of the association between variable response and model while removing the hypothesis (Hair et al., 2010). Table 7 represents a correlation between Internal Branding and Brand Endorsement at 5% level of significance the correlation is 64%. Here, the adjusted R square is 0.410, which tells about 41% variation of the dependent variable is explained by independent variables included in this model.

R-square as low as 10 per cent is widely accepted (Falk and Miller ,1992) for arts, humanities, and social science studies because human actions cannot be predicted reliably, so a small R-square is also not a problem in arts, humanities , and social science studies. In academic work focusing on marketing concerns, Hair et al., (2011) & Hair et al., (2013) proposed R2 values of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25 for endogenous variable variables could be defined as significant, moderate, or weak, as a simple rule of thumb respectively.

Table: 8 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.602	1	23.602	78.823	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.237	111	.299		
	Total	56.840	112			

a. Dependent Variable: BE

b. Predictors: (Constant), IBBE

Hair et al., (2010) states that the p-value must be below 0.05 to denote a statistically significant model, and that the above Table 8 indicates the Sig. value is 0.00 showing the particular relevance of this model. The ANOVA Table 8 apprises the significance level is 0.000 ($p = .000$), which is less than 0.05. Therefore, there is a statistically significant relationship between Internal Branding and Brand Endorsement. Thus, it demonstrates that in general, Internal Branding of different service-oriented organizations of Bangladesh has significant relevance with Brand Endorsement.

Table 9: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	3.702	.264		14.019	.000					
IBBE	.377	.042	.644	8.878	.000	.644	.644	.644	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: BE

The coefficient Table 9 tells the significant regression coefficients is Internal Branding ($p=0.000$). The VIF and Tolerance value that multicollinearity does not exist as the VIF and Tolerance values are 1.00, which are lower than 10. Here it has been clearly stating that Internal Branding is the most significant on Brand Endorsement.

Table 10: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Sig.	Accepted/Rejected
H1: Internal Communication has an influence on Brand Endorsement	.011	Accepted
H2: Training has an influence on Brand Endorsement	.220	Rejected
H3: Management support has an influence on Brand Endorsement	.000	Accepted
H4: Senior Leadership has an influence on Brand Endorsement	.699	Rejected
H5: Teamwork has an influence on Brand Endorsement	.222	Rejected
H6: Brand Knowledge has an influence on Brand Endorsement	.011	Accepted
H7: Internal Branding influences employees' Brand Endorsement	.000	Accepted

6. Conclusion

A successful internal branding program results in the brand being alive among employees as well as the company's other stakeholders (Du Preez and Bendixen, 2015). As a response, it is paramount that organizational employees understand and believe the brand values and behave accordingly to reinforce brand relevance and promise (Punjaisri et al., 2008). According to Wallace and De Chernatony (2011), internal branding interventions are often conceptualized as a top-down strategy consisting of low involvement from the employees' perspective while designing the relevant process and practices. This in

turn creates resistance from the employees towards the actions needed to attain the brand message. As a result, the findings highlight the importance of management support in influencing brand endorsement.

Suomi et al. (2019) posited that corporate culture, leadership, and management strategies are seen as essential factors in employee engagement with the brand in the health services sector. With this as a backdrop, the current study's findings emphasize the importance of management support in shaping the brand endorsing actions of service professionals. As a result, it is recommended that the organization's management responsibly craft brand commitments that employees can support and offer meaningfully to consumers (Walden et al., 2018). This allows management to create a robust internal branding process consistent with the organization's human resources practices.

7. Future Research Directions

The central focus of the paper was on internal branding interventions considering six major service-oriented organizations in a single geographical region in Bangladesh. The survey calls for further studies, analyzing the subject matter in a particular service field, to increase the generalization of research findings. Besides, scholars in the internal branding literature will benefit from assessing a system using CFA analysis or some other suitable statistical treatment. Furthermore, in order to assess the influence of internal branding on employees' brand endorsement behavior, moderating and mediating effects could be investigated.

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